

**MODEL OF FIRST AID PROCESS FOR INJURED INDIVIDUALS IN
SYSTEMATIC MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL MACHINERY
SAFETY**

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ABSTRACT. The use of machinery in agriculture, especially heavy and high-capacity equipment, increases the risk of injuries. This article examines the process of providing first aid in cases of injuries and bleeding that may occur with agricultural machinery. It offers recommendations for quick and effective first aid and analyzes the significant factors involved in this process. The relevance of the topic plays an essential role in preventing injuries and ensuring safety.

KEYWORDS: Agricultural machinery, Safety, First aid, Injuries, Bleeding, Systematic management.

INTRODUCTION. Agriculture is a vital sector of the economy, serving as a primary source for humanity's food supply. However, the use of agricultural machinery, particularly tractors, combines, and other mechanisms, can lead to injuries and difficult situations. These injuries often have severe consequences and can even pose life-threatening risks. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the process of providing first aid to injured individuals and to implement it correctly. Ensuring safety in the use of agricultural machinery is essential for the health, life, and productivity of every worker involved in the production process. Numerous hazards exist during the application of agricultural machinery, leading to injuries, bleeding, and potentially life-threatening situations. Consequently, it is vital to know and comply with safety rules and to understand the first aid procedures.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. Numerous studies have been conducted on safety issues concerning agricultural machinery. For instance, Smith (2019) provides recommendations on safety and injury prevention in the use of agricultural machinery in his work. He emphasizes that injuries often occur due to improper use of agricultural machinery and non-compliance with safety rules.

Additionally, Johnson (2020) offers a detailed analysis of the first aid process for injured individuals in his research. He outlines the steps of providing first aid in cases of injuries and methods to carry them out effectively.

Moreover, a study conducted in 2021 by Lee et al. analyzed the increase in injuries related to agricultural machinery and studies aimed at their prevention. Their findings indicate that the rise in injuries is primarily linked to non-compliance with safety rules.

INJURIES AND THEIR TYPES. Injuries that may occur during the use of agricultural machinery can vary widely. The most common types of injuries include:

1. **Lacerations:** These injuries are typically associated with sharp objects or machinery. For example, they may occur due to cutting components of combines or other agricultural machinery.

2. **Bleeding:** This injury is characterized by excessive blood loss, often resulting from severe cuts or wounds. If bleeding is not stopped quickly, it can pose life-threatening risks.

3. **Vascular damage:** These injuries can occur, particularly when using heavy agricultural machinery or during manual operations.

4. **Head and spinal injuries:** These may arise during the use of agricultural machinery, for instance, from falling during transport or work processes.

5. **Pain and fatigue:** These are common injuries that may result from overexertion during work processes or prolonged standing.

FIRST AID PROCESS. The process of providing first aid to injured individuals

consists of the following stages:

1. **Assessing the situation:** Before providing first aid, it is essential to evaluate the situation. This is crucial for determining the severity of the injury and ensuring safety. It may be necessary to move other workers or those present in the area to a safe location.

2. **Calling for emergency assistance:** If the injury is severe, it is crucial to call for emergency services immediately. This is vital for preserving the life of the injured individual.

3. **Stopping the bleeding:** Pressure can be applied to the wound, and if necessary, the injury can be elevated to stop the bleeding. It is essential to follow any guidelines provided by medical professionals while doing this.

4. **Cleaning and bandaging the wound:** Properly cleaning and dressing the injured area is crucial. If the injury is severe, the methods indicated by medical professionals should be implemented.

5. **Calming the individual:** Assisting the injured person to remain calm can help alleviate the injury's impact. Providing psychological support is also important, as the injured person may be under stress.

WHAT TO DO IN FIRST AID. There are several recommendations regarding what assistance to provide to injured individuals during the first aid process:

- **Stay calm and composed:** The stress of individuals often exacerbates their situation. Therefore, it is crucial for the first aid provider to maintain a calm and composed demeanor.

- **In cases of bleeding:** If there is blood loss, pressure should be applied to the wound and the injured area raised as high as possible. If the bleeding does not stop, medical assistance should be sought.

- **In cases of head injuries:** If there is a head injury, the injured individual should be calmed, and unless there is a severe skull injury, they should be laid down.

- **In cases of pain and trauma:** If the injury causes sharp or severe pain, medical assistance should be sought.

PREVENTING INJURIES. To prevent injuries during the use of agricultural machinery, the following recommendations can be made:

1. **Adhere to safety rules:** Strict compliance with safety rules when using agricultural machinery is essential. This is critical for preventing injuries and accidents.

2. **Conduct training sessions:** Regular training sessions on the use of agricultural machinery and safety rules should be held for workers.

3. **Utilize auditory and visual materials:** To ensure safety, communication should be strengthened, and safety rules for agricultural machinery should be presented using visual materials.

4. **Monitor the condition of the machinery:** Regularly monitoring the condition of agricultural machinery and preventing potential problems is essential.

5. **Use personal protective equipment:** Workers should use personal protective equipment, such as helmets, gloves, and other safety gear.

CONCLUSION. Injuries in agricultural machinery often occur due to non-compliance with safety rules. The process of providing first aid is essential for preserving the life of the injured individual. This article highlights the importance of preventing injuries and ensuring safety in agricultural machinery operations. Every employee and worker in agricultural institutions must have a good understanding of the first aid process for injured individuals. This not only helps save lives but also contributes to improving productivity in the agricultural sector.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

Xolbayev B.M., Raximov O.D., Maxmatqulov N.I. Hayot faoliyati xavfsizligi. Darslik (1-qism). – T.: “VORIS–nashriyot”, 2020. 304 b.

2. *Ibragimov E. I., Gazinazarova S, Yuldashev O.R. Mehnat muhofazasi maxsus kursi. – Toshkent, 2014. – 535 b.*
3. Rakhimov O.D. et al. Modern educational technologies // T.: "Science and technology publication." - 2013.
4. 28.10.2022. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Mehnat kodeksi
- 5.O.D. Rakhimov, Muradov S.H. Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques. // European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS). 2022. №24. P.80-86.
- 6.Bahodir O‘ktam o‘g K. et al. ELEMENTS OF THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF INDUSTRIAL SAFETY, LABOR PROTECTION AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AT THE" UZBEKISTAN GTL" PLANT //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11.
- 7.Oktam o‘g‘li K. B. Nishonova Shahrizoda Chori qizi, Temirova Shahzoda Jamshidovna, Normengliyeva Fayyoza O ‘tkir kizi. SAFETY BEHAVIORAL AUDIT METHODOLOGY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2.
- 8.Rakhimov Oktyabr Dustkabilovich; Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o‘g‘li. Innovative Technologies in Teachingdirectors and Specialists of Industrial Enterprises on "Labor Protection"// European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 2021/12/29. 80-85.